

Malfunctions Occurring In Electric Resistance Steam Generators And Their Prevention

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Abstract:

This article analyzes the main faults that occur in electrical resistance steam generators and methods to combat them. Electrical resistance steam generators are widely used in industry and other sectors. However, various faults may arise during their operation. This article includes the identification of different faults, explanations of the factors that cause them, and recommendations for preventing them. It is shown that such faults can be minimized with the help of digital technologies and modernization.

Keywords: Electrical resistance steam generator, fault, prevention, maintenance, energy efficiency, startup issues.

INTRODUCTION.

systems, and other sectors to produce steam. They work by converting electrical energy into thermal energy through resistance, which generates steam. To ensure the efficiency and long-term operation of steam generators, it is important to continuously monitor their technical condition. However, certain faults may arise in steam generators. These faults can reduce the generator's efficiency, lead to resource wastage, and even cause safety issues. This article discusses the most common faults in electrical resistance steam generators and methods to combat them.

II. Methodology.

The analysis of faults and prevention methods presented in this article is based on practical data obtained from experienced specialists and scientific research. Using the gathered material, the following methods are employed to analyze faults:

1. Studying the working principle of steam generators.
2. Identifying the most common faults.

3. Analyzing the technical factors that cause faults.

4. Recommending the most effective maintenance methods to prevent faults.

An electrical steam generator is a small boiler that uses electrical energy to convert water into steam. Such steam generators have reached an advanced level and are being used as an efficient and reliable service system. Steam generators have become a trustworthy assistant in various industries in Europe, the Middle East, Southeast Asia, and other regions. Utilizing science and technology, industries are constantly developing and innovating to provide better steam generators and services.

The steam boiler is made from high-quality carbon steel or stainless steel. Modern electrical resistance steam generators are highly durable and are manufactured with excellent craftsmanship. The heat insulation covering of the steam boiler is made from high-quality heat-resistant materials. A high-pressure pump is used to supply water to the boiler in a short amount of time. The operating system is divided into automatic and semi-automatic control.

The water source is connected to the pump, and once the steam generator is connected to electrical power, it starts to generate steam after 30 minutes, producing steam at a pressure ranging from 0.4 MPa to 0.7 MPa.

Figure 1. Electrical resistance steam generator.

The electrical resistance steam generator requires the installation of a steam valve, safety net, pressure regulator, and pressure gauge. The pressure regulator is then connected to the steam generator system. The water pipe is connected to the water tank's inlet, and the float ball is installed in the water tank. The water supply valve is opened, and the water tank is connected to the automatic water level control system, and the pump is filled with water. To do this, the air is expelled from the pump by turning the vent valve.

Once the electrical power is turned on, the power switch on the steam generator is pressed to start it. The water supply indicator lights up, and the pump starts supplying water to the steam boiler. When the level relay detects the water level (when the water indicator reaches the standard value), it

switches off, and the heating indicator lights up. The steam pressure reaches the nominal value within 20-30 minutes. After that, the steam valve opens, and the steam can be used.

A semi-automatic electrical heater is operated manually for water addition, while the automatic control system has the same operating function.

III. Results

To extend the service life of the steam generator, it is necessary to use purified soft water as much as possible. Before connecting the water pipe, it should be washed once to remove impurities such as sand, stones, and iron. Deposits that can enter the water tank or pump may cause damage to the pump. A filter should be installed at the water intake to facilitate easy monitoring.

The power source voltage should be 220V/380V. If the error is significant, an automatic voltage stabilizer should be installed; otherwise, it may burn the equipment or reduce steam production.

The water tank should be drained once a day to prevent excessive sediment accumulation and clogging of the pipes. To ensure the normal operation of the machine and extend its service life, the water level control electrode, the inner part of the steam boiler, the electrical heating device, and the water tank should be cleaned once a month.

The steam pressure, set at 0.4 MPa or 0.7 MPa, should not be changed by the user. If sediment is detected inside the steam boiler after prolonged use, it should be cleaned before use.

Faults and methods of elimination.

Table 1:

Malfunction	Causes	Solutions
Steam generator does not work after	1. Damaged on/off switch 2. Faulty electrical cables	1. Replace the on/off switch. 2. Check power supply and wiring.

being turned on	3. Contactor not closed	3. Repair or replace the contactor.			2. Burnt coil 3. Damaged contacts	power-off. 2. Replace the coil or contactor. 3. Repair or replace the contacts.
Water pump not working	1. Blown fuse 2. Contactor contacts not closed 3. Impeller of the water pump is jammed 4. Water pump motor damaged or capacitor failed	1. Replace the fuse. 2. Repair or replace the contactor. 3. Clear obstructions or replace the impeller if damaged. 4. Repair the motor or replace the capacitor.		Low pull force of contactor contacts	1. Low power supply voltage 2. Contactor intermittently trips 3. Phase imbalance in a three-phase system	1. Check the power source voltage. 2. Use a stabilizer to increase voltage. 3. Adjust the phases as needed.
Insufficient water pressure or no water supply from the pump	1. Reversed water pump 2. Air in the pump system 3. Blocked water channel 4. Loose pump inlet	1. Check direction and adjust wiring as needed. 2. Release air from the system. 3. Remove obstructions. 4. Secure the pump inlet firmly.		Pump stops or fails to work	1. Faulty water level relay 2. Stuck or faulty contactor 3. Dirty liquid level electrodes	1. Replace the water level relay. 2. Repair or replace the contactor. 3. Clean the electrodes.
Slow heating or no heating	1. Faulty heater 2. Faulty contactor 3. Faulty water level relay 4. Abnormal power supply voltage	1. Replace the heater. 2. Repair or replace the contactor. 3. Consult an electrician. 4. Consult an electrician.		Low water pump pressure	1. Worn impeller 2. Worn pump 3. Air in the pump	1. Adjust clearance or replace the impeller. 2. Adjust clearance or replace the pump. 3. Remove air from the pump.
Contactor not working	1. Stuck contacts	1. Open contacts after		Steam generator water level	1. Reverse flow through check valve or solenoid valve	1. Replace the check valve or solenoid valve.

not maintained		
High or low steam pressure	1. Faulty pressure regulator	1. Replace with an equivalent pressure regulator.
Error in the electrical system	1. Low insulation resistance or overheating wire	1. Keep it dry and assign an electrician for repairs.
Water and steam leakage	1. Loose pipe connection or valve 2. Damaged pipe seals	1. Repair and secure connections or replace the valve. 2. Replace pipe seals.

IV. Discussion

It is important to introduce modern technologies to improve the efficiency of steam generators and prevent failures. Electric resistance generators usually operate at high temperatures and pressures, which requires special materials and technologies to ensure their operation. Automated control systems, high-quality components, and systematic maintenance help prevent failures.

Also, after the introduction of steam generator maintenance and monitoring systems, the possibility of preventing failures and their rapid detection increases. This helps to ensure long-term operation and high efficiency of generators.

V. Conclusion.

After learning about the main failures that occur in electric resistance steam generators and methods for combating them, we can say that maintenance, automated control systems, and the use of high-quality materials are necessary to

prevent failures. These methods ensure the reliability and long-term operation of generators and increase energy efficiency.

In the future, with further development of steam generator technology, new approaches and innovative solutions are expected to be introduced to prevent failures and increase operating efficiency.

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